

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure
PLUS

Assessment of international standardisation and harmonisation of environmental observation: eLTER RI Standard Observations Protocols

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1 Summary

This document describes the efforts made to create SO protocols for the eLTER RI, and set them in context among the wider landscape of environmental monitoring, including efforts at harmonisation, and should be read alongside the overview of the selection process for the SO variables covered in Zacharias et al. (2024). The eLTER RI Standard Observations protocols establish a comprehensive framework for standardised environmental monitoring across eLTER sites. Through a systematic evaluation process, high-priority variables were selected from a long-list of 173 candidates, organised across five spheres: Atmosphere, Biosphere, Geosphere, Hydrosphere, and Sociosphere.

The Standard Observation (SO) framework adopts a balanced approach between standardisation and flexibility, acknowledging the diverse nature of eLTER sites while establishing common baseline measurements - an approach of being as standardised as possible, and as flexible as necessary. A key challenge lies in legacy data integration and cross-network compatibility in terms of protocols. Considerable efforts have been made to provide flexible approaches to harmonisation across diverse habitat types and monitoring traditions, respecting the high degree of network co-location with the UNECE ICPs, ICOS, SITES and other research infrastructures (RIs), and adapting protocols to the broad habitat coverage required in the eLTER RI. The SO protocols implement standardised data and metadata standards, and a common vocabulary for consistent terminology, which requires translation efforts from existing RI protocols. The SO framework also includes mechanisms for continuous improvement through regular protocol revisions (via Thematic Service Areas TSA02 and TSA03), building in adaptability in terms of emerging technologies and methodologies. The SO protocols represent a significant step toward creating an environmental monitoring system that provides a robust foundation for generating the standardised, high-quality data essential for both research and policy-making purposes.

2 Introduction

The eLTER Research Infrastructure (RI) builds upon the established LTER-Europe network of sites and platforms, which has been instrumental in integrating traditional environmental monitoring approaches with whole system ecosystem research that also considers human interactions with the environment. This initiative encompasses over 500 long-term ecological research sites including more than 50 larger Long-Term Socio-Ecological Research (LTSER) platforms, spanning diverse ecosystems from urban to rural settings. This basis is developed in the eLTER RI to become a network that is:

- Long-term: aims to collect, record, synthesise and make available information that documents long-term trends of ecosystems
- In-Situ: aims to collect and make available data on different spatial scales and for different ecosystem compartments of individual in-natura sites
- Process focussed: aims to identify and quantify interactions of ecosystem processes affected by external and internal drivers
- Whole System Approach: aims to provide a comprehensive description of the whole ecosystem including ecosystem processes, cycles, and human interactions.

By providing a robust infrastructure for long-term observations, the eLTER RI will generate the data necessary for understanding complex human-nature interactions and their implications for ecosystem integrity and services. A key feature of this is harmonising and applying standard observation protocols across the network, an effort informed by lessons learned from other

established research infrastructures. By borrowing successful methodologies from sibling environmental monitoring networks and integrating them into its own protocols, eLTER can provide standardised data that is essential for cross-comparative studies and effective policy-making. Here, we review the evolution of the eLTER RI, and examine how eLTER's SO protocols have been developed through a combination of insights gained from other networks and tailored to meet the specific needs of the eLTER RI. We also aim to provide insights that can facilitate collaborative research efforts among environmental monitoring networks.

Table 1: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ACTRIS	Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution
DEIMS	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio- ecological systems Research
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICP	UNECE International Cooperative Programme
ILTER	International Long-term Ecological Research
LTSER	Long-term Socio-ecological Research
MSE	Macrosystems Ecology
NEON	US National Ecological Observatory Network
PPD	Press Pulse Dynamic Model
QA/QC	Quality assurance/quality control
RI	Research Infrastructure
SO(P)	Standard Observation (Protocol)
SPF	Sites and Platform forum
TERENO	German Terrestrial Environmental Observatories
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
VRP	Verifiable Regional Prediction
WAILS	Whole-system Approach for In-situ research on Life Supporting systems

3 eLTER network overview

The history leading up to the eLTER RI is important to understand as it has an influence on issues of standardisation and harmonisation. From individual sites to the RI level, the structure has been best understood as a network of networks, with a strong bottom up influence. Rather than beginning with a centralised plan, leadership and funding and then finding locations where this plan can be implemented (such as the U.S National Science Foundation's National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON)), the eLTER RI has its roots in existing national networks, which came together in LTER Europe. Many of the participating sites were also active long before the formation of LTER Europe in 2007, bringing important time series of data gathered according to a variety of protocols. In many cases these go back to the 1990s, 1980s or even earlier. While the “top-down” approach of a project such as NEON clearly facilitates standardisation, the bottom-up approach of eLTER brings a different set of strengths (and challenges). An existing community and organisational structures were available to engage in the building of an RI, long-time series of data are already available rather than having to wait for years to identify trends, and much of the required investment to establish sites has already been made. On the other hand, the clear disadvantage is that a range of national methodologies need to be adapted to a standardised approach going forward, to the greatest extent that this is possible (Mirtl et al. 2018).

There is a high degree of colocation of sites between European monitoring networks. Based on information in the DEIMS SDR registry (and noting that information on affiliations beyond eLTER here is only partial and so very likely to be an underestimate) over 100 sites are also part of the UNECE ICP Forests network, 38 are part of ICOS, and other networks are also well represented (Table 2).

Table 2: Examples of RI co-locations with eLTER according to the DEIMS registry (not an exhaustive list)

Research infrastructure/Network	Number of co-located eLTER sites
ICP Forests	114
ICOS	38
ICP Waters	15
ICP Integrated Monitoring	14
Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW)	12
SITES	9
Lifeplan*	5
ACTRIS	3

**Lifeplan is a time limited project rather than an RI*

Each of these RI/networks has its own focal area, and a set of variables appropriate to its goals are measured. There is however a degree of overlap, with some variables being of interest to several RIs, although methods often vary. For example, meteorological data is often gathered at sites, but the method varies depending on the research focus - a higher frequency and resolution may be demanded where these measurements are part of a site's key focus, such as at ICOS stations.

The unique position the future eLTER RI marks in the environmental monitoring landscape is largely based on the WAILES concept - Whole-system Approach for In-situ research on Life Supporting systems (Mirtl et al., in prep). The WAILES concept combines two overarching concepts: the Press

Pulse Dynamic Model (PPD) (Collins et al., 2011) and the study of Macrosystems Ecology (MSE) (Heffernan et al., 2014). Briefly, the PPD model is an iterative framework which aims to identify linkages between the sociosphere with its surrounding geo-, hydro-, bio and atmosphere. In other words, it identifies how human behaviour inflicts both press disturbances (e.g., land use, land fragmentation) and pulses (e.g., floods, nutrient input) onto ecosystem processes which in turn alter ecosystem services. Changes in ecosystem services will again alter human behaviour initiating iterative feedbacks between society and its environment. Macrosystems Ecology (MSE) connects multiple temporal and spatial scales thus bridging the gap between analyses at community level to large scale ecosystem level patterns. The integration of both frameworks ensures a holistic approach to ecosystem monitoring of biotic and abiotic fluxes and states while simultaneously capturing the societal-ecosystem feedbacks and interactions on large temporal and geographical scales.

3.1 eLTER network organisation and link to SOs

The eLTER RI as a consolidation of 26 national networks is embedded in a large geographical area ranging over multiple biogeographical regions (see Figure 1) and ecosystem types. Further, individual research stations vary in available infrastructure and instrumentation providing several challenges to ongoing standardization efforts (see below). The SOs are designed (Zacharias, 2024) to address such variability by offering different degrees of measurement accuracy as well as spatial and temporal resolution.

- Prime method: highest measurement effort and thus highest eLTER standard possible reflected by this method
- Basic method: less complex measurement effort resulting in reduced costs for individual stations

To help navigate through the heterogeneous research and monitoring landscape, the RI is structured on different hierarchical levels.

- eLTER Sites will be labelled by categories
 - Category 1: highest level of instrumentation and capability of covering a whole system approach (WAILS) for all spheres and selected SOs at least with the basic method. Further, sites will have an emphasis on at least two spheres which will be covered by prime methods and protocols.
 - Category 2: the whole system approach is fulfilled on a basic level, sites cover all spheres and selected SOs with the basic method.
- eLTSER Platforms: have focus on transdisciplinary, long-term socio-ecological research and act as living labs for the implementation of the WAILS whole system approach. The research focus is at a landscape scale and in close collaboration with local and regional stakeholders. A platform needs to include at least one category 2 eLTER Site.

The above discussed criteria serve as a short overview and mainly refer to the planned implementation of SOs at different site categories. For a more detailed description, including examples and a discussion of the consideration of costs see Zacharias. et al. (2024).

Figure 1: Overview of LTER Europe sites in different biogeographical regions (Mollenhauer et al., 2018).

4 eLTER Standard Observations

4.1 Development Process

The following is a very brief overview of how the variables to be included in the SOs were decided upon. For a more detailed account of the process leading to the definition of the eLTER SOs, see Zacharias. et al. (2024). It is also important to stress that the SOs initially implemented in the RI are intended as a first set which will be revised and complemented with further variables in an iterative improvement process as the RI grows and develops over time. We are acutely aware that new developments in monitoring are ongoing e.g. in biodiversity monitoring making use of new sensors and AI allowing automated species detection and identification. This will be considered as well even in established SOs. As a result of the consultation and discussion process (as outlined in Figure 2), 173 variables were identified as candidates for inclusion. These were then submitted to a ranking process (Figure 3) based on criteria of relevance (how well they represent key elements of the ecosystem integrity concept; and how well they function as a response to drivers of environmental change), cost efficiency, and operative efficiency (possible to apply at many sites, using well-established standards).

Figure 2: the process leading to adoption of the SO framework

On this basis, 76 variables were rated as high priority, which became part of the eLTER Standard Observations (many SOs such as Meteorology are composed of several variables, see Figure 4). These SOs were then divided into “spheres” according to which part of the socio-ecological system they were most relevant to (from the categories of Atmosphere, Biosphere, Geosphere, Hydrosphere and Sociosphere).

Figure 3. Definition of Standard Observations (variable + method + protocol) based on consideration of scientific relevance, cost and operative feasibility

Figure 4: Example of a Standard Observation bundle comprised of multiple variables, see eLTER Information Sheet #30 (note that this is a general example of the structure and some details may have changed by the final version of this SO bundle)

4.2 Coordination of the writing process

Beginning with the agreed upon list of SOs, the written work on the protocols was structured in a top-down manner organised by the five spheres listed above (Atmo-, Bio-, Hydro-, Geo- and Sociosphere). Each of the spheres were assigned a co-ordinator (or “sphere lead”) represented by a leading expert in each domain. This role was intended to fill several functions all aimed at facilitating the writing work on the protocols. In close cooperation with the T3.3 coordination, sphere leads

were responsible for recruiting the writing teams for each SO (or SO bundle) and structuring the work on the different SOs. Additionally, sphere leads served as a first hand quality control on the resulting protocol drafts during an initial round of review.

SO writing teams were composed of experts in their field with most frequently one leading author and a small number of contributing authors. Efforts to find such expert volunteers were made through repeated calls in the extended eLTER network. Where possible, the aim was to include a wide range of different viewpoints, institutions, and countries from experts within each field. In this way some of the potential controversies and disagreements could be discussed at an early stage, with the aim of producing a draft protocol that could be widely accepted. Once first drafts were ready, a review process was initiated by inviting comments and contributions from the eLTER community and other external experts identified by sphere leads or the coordination team. Some specifically targeted groups in the eLTER community to invite for feedback included:

- Sites and Platform forum (SPF)
- Expert Groups
- National coordinators

Finally, feedback was incorporated by authors into a first complete version based on a provided template.

4.3 Borrowed Protocols and Methodologies

A general principle aim when writing SO protocols for eLTER was not to create novel approaches (unless needed) but to adopt or adapt tried and tested protocols that were already in use within other research infrastructures. Given the high degree of colocation with other RIs (Table 2), the desire to minimise costs for sites when becoming part of the eLTER RI, and the aim of harmonising protocols with other RIs, there were some obvious candidates for protocols that could be adopted/adapted.

4.3.1 UNECE ICPs (Forests, Integrated Monitoring, Waters)

Even prior to the development of the eLTER SO protocols, the ICP protocols had already been widely used at eLTER Sites due to a high degree of co-location between the networks (Table 1). Apart from cost and practicality advantages, this also means that existing long time series of data for many key variables can be continued in the eLTER RI with minimal harmonisation issues. The ICP manuals were the starting point for many SOs within the Atmosphere, Biosphere, Geosphere, and Hydrosphere categories. These ICP networks are focussed on the effects of atmospheric pollutant deposition and measure a wide range of variables related to air quality/atmospheric deposition and both chemical responses (soil and water chemistry) and biological responses (vegetation communities, tree growth, aquatic biota).

4.3.2 ICOS

The ICOS protocols, with their focus on greenhouse gas concentrations and carbon fluxes, were an important resource for above all the Atmosphere SOs. ICOS also has the second highest number of co-locations with eLTER sites (after the ICPs). Many of the ICOS protocols labelled as auxiliary variables were also highly relevant for the eLTER SOs, often complementing the ICP protocols for application in non-forest habitats.

4.3.3 Lifeplan

Although a time limited project rather than a research infrastructure or permanent network, Lifeplan protocols were an important resource for several Biosphere SOs with a focus on newer methods for monitoring biodiversity such as eDNA, camera traps and audio recording in combination with

advanced machine learning/AI methods. There are few eLTER Sites that are already measuring these variables, so there is more freedom to choose appropriate methods without having to account for existing monitoring infrastructure or long time series that have already been collected.

4.3.4 Others

Although the above protocols from other RIs were the most widely used they are by no means the only sources that were relied upon. Protocols from the World Meteorological Organisation, the EU Water Framework Directive, SoilBON, TERENO, ACTRIS, SITES, INBO and others also played an important role in the writing process for selected SOs. Further, particularly with regard to socio-economic and demographic data, since European Union data (e.g., Eurostats) and nationally compiled data will be used as SOs for those categories, their protocols are de facto also adopted.

4.3.5 ISO Standards

ISO standards were extensively referred to in the SO protocols but at a more granular level than the whole SO protocol. For example, an ISO method for measuring levels of a chemical parameter may be recommended, but there is no ISO for monitoring throughfall deposition of atmospheric pollutants.

In all cases, writing teams working on SOs were provided with relevant sample protocols from other RIs and strongly encouraged to rely upon existing protocols wherever possible.

4.4 Rationale for adopting specific protocols

An obvious factor here was cost and practicality - if a method is already widely used then the presumption was to incorporate it into the SOs protocol unless there were good reasons to do otherwise.

Many SOs specify both a basic and a prime method, which relates to the site categorisation. The prime methods involve some combination of more frequent sampling or measurement, the use of more precise equipment, or taking in situ measurements instead of retrieving data from other sources. Consequently it was often considered most appropriate to ground the basic method and the prime method on different existing protocols. For example in the meteorology SO bundle, the basic method allows retrieval from a nearby station (outside the site) while the prime method requires high frequency onsite measurements and leans on the WMO and ICOS protocols.

Figure 5: Overview of SO protocols which are partly or completely adopted from established protocols in sister RI

5 Harmonisation, standardisation, and eLTER Standard Observations

5.1 Alignment with Existing Standards

The harmonisation of existing methodologies is characterised by the bottom-up manner in which LTER sites and national networks have been developed. LTER and co-located sites were established with different research and monitoring strategies in mind and their design is motivated by institutional and program-related requirements and other local and national considerations. As a consequence, the sites are characterised by a wide variety of individual site measurement variables, ecosystem types, infrastructures and instrumentation providing a challenge in transforming the resulting output into large scale comparable monitoring data (Mollenhauer et al., 2018).

To address this challenge, a top-down harmonisation and agreement on common parameters and methods were necessary to achieve comparable baseline data. Here, a fine balance needs to be struck between defining a common standard for all measurements while still permitting enough flexibility to acknowledge site-specific needs (Holtzer et al. 2018). The resulting harmonisation of existing and established methods in the SO protocol is thus a pragmatic attempt at gathering comparable and integrable datasets while coming as close as possible to having one method as the standard.

5.2 Integration of Challenges and Solutions

5.2.1 Habitat types

One issue that arose repeatedly is that the eLTER aims to cover a wide variety of habitat types, whereas the most suitable or widely used existing protocol is sometimes focussed on a much narrower range of habitats. For example, the UNECE ICP protocols (ICP Forests, ICP Integrated Monitoring and ICP Waters) were used as source material in many SOs, however, for terrestrial variables these are designed entirely with forests in mind. In some cases alternative protocols were available for other habitats, but simply directly adopting those would present the same quandary, as many eLTER Sites are actually located in forests. The solution here was most often to base the SO protocol on ICP manuals and add material from another source to be applied in other habitat types (e.g. the ICOS auxiliary measurements protocols).

5.2.2 Legacy data

The history of eLTER as a bottom-up network of LTER Europe sites (Haase et al., 2016) caused difficulties when considering how to specify a SO protocol in many cases. A majority of SOs cover variables that many sites have been measuring for years or in some cases many decades before the idea of building the eLTER RI was formed. Sites following national protocols or protocols of other RIs or networks for these variables are understandably cautious about applying new methods, either replacing the previous method (and so harming time series continuity) or complementing it (with added effort and expense). While widely used protocols were adopted where possible in writing the SO protocols, these are almost never universally used and this implies some level of difficulty to some sites. However, in a few cases these difficulties proved insurmountable, most notably in the ground vegetation SO. Inventories of vegetation communities have a long and diverse history in Europe, and many sites have multi-decadal time series of data gathered according to a wide range of national methodologies. Apart from a general unwillingness to break continuity of these time series, in most cases there was no obvious candidate protocol in such wide use as to be an obvious suggestion for a standard method. After much discussion a new protocol was written to apply at sites joining the RI which have not previously inventoried ground vegetation, but data will be submitted to the RI from existing monitoring according to the existing protocols, with harmonisation being done at a database level. This was the most extreme example of the bottom up difficulties, but in many cases a greater degree of flexibility is allowed in the protocols than would ideally be the case for producing

standardised data (compared for instance to a top down RI building a new network from the ground up, such as NEON). A very strong top-down standardisation would inevitably severely limit the number of sites willing and able to participate in the RI, but standardisation is at the same time required to distinguish the eLTER RI from the looser bottom up network of LTER Europe. In many ways, the story of this tension in writing the SO protocols can be summed up as “as standardised as possible, as flexible as necessary”, but finding the right balance is a constant challenge.

5.2.3 Differences in measurement techniques

Different sensors and equipment may produce measurements that are not directly comparable, even for the same variable, and sites may have long-term datasets collected with older equipment (or a range of equipment over time). Going forward, the SO protocols specify the requirements for equipment to be used (while not mandating a specific model), but intercalibration is required where data collected with different equipment will be combined. If a site is adopting new methods for the eLTER SOs it is recommended to run both old and new methods in parallel until calibrations can be made. Where it has proven impossible to adopt SO protocols in international monitoring due to existing commitments to national protocols and long time series (such as in the Water Framework Directive), extensive efforts in intercalibration have been needed (Poikane, 2015), highlighting the importance of standardising equipment and methods as much as possible from the start.

5.2.4 Taxonomic issues

Many eLTER Sites have long-term datasets collected using different taxonomic standards. These may use outdated or inconsistent taxonomic classifications, which often do not align with current standards. The eLTER RI requires submitted data to be aligned with the GBIF backbone (GBIF, 2024) for taxonomy, which will ideally be facilitated by automated tools to check submitted taxonomic data for errors and outdated names. Legacy data may be submitted which use other taxonomies but these must be clearly stated in the accompanying metadata to facilitate harmonisation. There are numerous software tools available in R and Python that guide users in matching species names with reference databases (in this case the GBIF backbone), tools which are needed to evaluate, and edit taxonomic information in datasets that are too large for manual revisions (Grenié et al., 2023). Such tools also increase the reproducibility of the process, as long as users fully document their workflow (including which package and version, which functions, and the database versions that are used as a reference).

5.2.5 Semantics and standardised vocabularies

By bringing together material from a range of existing protocols, and incorporating legacy data from sites with a long operational history, there is a great potential for confusion based on unclear use of terms. A basic concept such as a “plot” can have quite different definitions in different contexts, and there was an urgent need to use language in a clear and standardised manner when writing the SO protocols. The solution was to align on the eLTER vocabularies, existing and newly developed. Already existing was EnvThes, which compiles a set of terms in order to describe in a harmonised way data resulting from observations and measurements across different domains (used by DEIMS-SDR) and eLTER_CL, a thesaurus for controlled lists used by the eLTER community. A thesaurus for SOs was also introduced, and extensive efforts were made to ensure consistency despite the SO protocols leaning on a diverse range of existing material. Each SO protocol has a table for metadata, populated by relevant variables from a standard list (e.g. geographical coverage information, or details of the licence under which data and metadata are made available). There is also a data table for each SO, which specifies the required information and format for all relevant measurements.

Table 3: Example of current semantics structure for individual SOs in EnvThes

eLTER sphere	Standard Observation	SO variables
Atmosphere URI: https://vocabs.lter-europe.net/so/c5	SOATM_027	Air relative humidity
	Meteorological data	Precipitation amount
	URI: https://vocabs.lter-europe.net/so/027	Air temperature
		Wind speed
		Wind direction
		Surface air pressure

5.2.6 Harmonising data formats and metadata standards

A key tool for moving from a diversity of formats for both data and metadata to developing a standard format for the eLTER RI has been the first call for data. This process is ongoing at the time of writing (late 2024), but the aim is to encourage and allocate funding to sites that own data on a selection of key SO variables to submit this to the eLTER database in early 2025. Standard data and metadata templates are provided that will also be suitable for ongoing data submission in future, and submitted legacy data needs to be formatted to the specified standards. The legacy data offered has been gathered according to a wide variety of protocols over many years, and represents a harmonisation challenge that will be repeated for most SOs in due course, with all of the challenges described elsewhere in this document. By beginning as early as possible with this kind of real world task, the key areas where extra guidance will be needed for data providers can be identified and training and support offered. At the same time, the submission and harmonisation processes at the central database level can be adjusted based on lessons learned. Although it is still too early in this process to draw concrete conclusions, a flexible approach to revising procedures as needed will result in a solid and well-tested routine for submitting data in a standardised manner when the whole RI is operational.

The current data and metadata format is based on eLTER field specifications for data reporting (templates can be found at doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6373410). These are in turn harmonised with Darwin Core (Wieczorek, 2012) where possible/relevant.

5.3 Innovative Approaches

In some cases, the implementation of rather new methods avoided the difficulties around dealing with numerous existing protocols outlined in the previous section. For these SOs, rather than an abundance of competing candidate protocols, there was a need to decide on the best way to implement (new) methods that are not yet widely used in the context of standardised and long-term data collection. These SOs are in two groups - the sociosphere, and newer methods in biodiversity monitoring. The former is part of an outstanding feature of eLTER, the whole system approach.

5.3.1 Novel socio-ecological methods

eLTER's implementation of socio-ecological SO generally aims at describing human-nature interactions, as well as demographic and socio-economic parameters, among others covering land use, resource use, governance and ecosystem services. On the one hand, this is achieved by retrieval of European, national or site-specific statistics. In the case of European statistics, data will be

collected and processed in a centralised data service provided by the RI, for example coupled with “cookie-cutter” tools to delimit the area of interest.

On the other hand, novel socio-ecological methods are developed for some SOs, for which deployment in the eLTER RI will serve as a case study. These include SOSOC_032 Governance structure and character, SOSOC_037 Land use, SOSOC_040 Ecosystem services profile, and SOSOC_114 Livestock. These SOs will be collected by implementing site-specific expert assessments, surveys and interview panels for which there are established methods in the field of research but no tradition of standardised protocols. Here, the work done in eLTER is groundbreaking and will help advance the methods in this field of research and their application on a European scale.

5.3.2 New methods to address biodiversity decline

Biotic parameters often have a long observation history in the respective countries and the resulting data are difficult to obtain in a standardised and taxonomically rich format. Further, the spatio-temporal resolution of traditional methods come at a high cost tradeoff. The eLTER SOs focusing on biodiversity measurements thus implement novel methods to measure biodiversity on a large-scale deployment across Europe in a cost-effective manner.

Such novel methods include acoustic recording for insects, amphibians, birds and bats. Acoustic recordings are highly promising for these taxonomic groups with the extended future implementation of AI to identify species abundances. An EuropaBON expert group assessed the feasibility and readiness of this method and ranked the use of acoustic recording to be highly attainable for the listed taxa groups (Dornelas et al., 2023). The eLTER RI will play a central role in implementing acoustic recordings on a European scale and further progressing this method.

Automated sampling of insects via Malaise traps and the use of molecular (e.g. metabarcoding of Malaise samples and eDNA) methods further make use of automated and large scale standardization efforts. While considering the disadvantages of metabarcoding methods such as the lack of abundance data, it offers a higher taxonomic resolution and large-scale non-invasive application while significantly reducing processing costs.

Despite ongoing advances and development for metabarcoding methods in the past decade, some challenges remain regarding transnational laboratory standardization guidelines and the establishment of proper reference libraries (Deiner et al., 2021). While there are several initiatives to achieve a consensus on common standards, eLTER plays an important part in aligning these guidelines and testing them on a large scale.

Another aspect of data management is related to the recording and transmission of measurements, where there is the possibility to incorporate digital tools such as smartphone applications into the sample and data management workflows. This can increase both efficiency and traceability, as well as interoperability where an application is in use in another RI (e.g. Lifeplan). Where appropriate, such tools and workflows will be incorporated into eLTER SO protocols.

5.4 Data Management and Interoperability

Data produced through SO protocols can be sample, sensor and retrieval based. In the current efforts of the data mobilization task targeting existing legacy data, PLUS WP7 & 14 aim to prepare and upload data to the central Digital Asset Registry (DAR) using key SO data types, i.e. SOATM_027 - Meteorology, SOBIO_017 - Vegetation composition, SOBIO_096 - Surface water – Algae, SOHYD_004 - Physical/chemical characteristics standing waters and SOHYD_168 - Soil water content and temperature, from partnering sites and platforms across the RI. The data targeted with the above listed data types are sensor and sample based and are linked to four out of the five spheres. These serve as a test case to establish future workflows for the data management Topic Center and associated services. The Sociosphere key data types, e.g. population density and land use categories, are mainly retrieval based data and will be mobilized in a separate effort together with the sphere

leads and system developers to establish robust, automatized and long-lasting workflows. Sensor and sample based data within the data mobilization task can either be uploaded directly to the eLTER DAR through an ingest portal or in a separate workflow through national network specific Application Programming Interface (API) by harvesting data and metadata from national nodes. These data and metadata harvesting tools can then be further developed and used to exchange data between eLTER and other international RIs. Additional metadata information will be assigned to data uploads by interlinking DEIMS and the eLTER DAR as well as linking data types with the SO vocabulary and eLTER EnvThes for additional semantics required to describe the data, e.g. keywords, etc.

When the data mobilization task has successfully embedded workflows for sensor, sample and retrieval based key data types, these workflows can then be further developed and used to continue the work on additional SO data.

5.5 Cross-Network Collaboration

A high degree of influence from other RI networks is already apparent in the adoption and adaption of a wide range of existing protocols in the eLTER SOs, a process inspired by the considerable physical co-location between these monitoring networks. While this is a great advantage for building the eLTER RI, it can in no way reduce the need for collaboration between the existing sibling RIs and eLTER. Each RI is designed to address specific scientific objectives, and integration of their outputs in harmonised datasets can provide a more comprehensive understanding of environmental systems than any RI can reach alone. While RIs apply their own standard observations and protocols, the effort required to integrate data from entities using standardised, well documented methods across their sites and supporting the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles is vastly less than where this is not the case. Integrating legacy data from national monitoring schemes for example, can be a challenging and extremely time consuming task in comparison.

Collaboration can be seen at both site and network levels. By participating in multiple networks, sites gain access to infrastructure, standardised QA/QC procedures, and FAIR-compliant data handling procedures. These in turn facilitate cross-network collaboration and data harmonisation, and enhance the scientific value of site-level observations by enabling their use in broader analyses, such as verifiable regional predictions (VFRs) and policy-relevant indicators. VFRs are identified by Futter, et al. (2023) as an example of the high impact science that can be produced by collaboration between RIs. These can combine site based observations with modelling and/or remote sensing that requires ground truthing to produce indicators (such as critical loads for acidification and eutrophication) that have seamless regional spatial coverage and a high policy relevance. Long-term legacy observations from sites or networks where monitoring began decades ago can be combined with real-time data to improve temporal coverage and validate emerging trends or parameterise models predicting future developments. This reciprocity strengthens all networks involved by expanding their analytical capabilities and increasing the impact of their findings. By integrating the sociosphere with observations from the natural science spheres, the eLTER platforms have a especially strong potential to increase the range of questions that can be asked and answered and the policy relevance of both eLTER and other collaborating RIs.

If the potential offered by sharing of open data created with clearly defined standard protocols is to be fully realised, it is critical that an atmosphere of continuous collaboration is created or maintained between eLTER and other RIs. This is not only a matter of formal agreements and technical solutions (although these are of course needed) but also a less tangible matter of creating and maintaining goodwill and being seen as a “good citizen” in the RI landscape, offering clear mutual benefits to RIs engaging in co-operative undertakings. These benefits can be e.g. opportunities for participation in joint projects, developing/implementing novel and innovative methods, sharing data citations and available legacy data among the RIs as well as joint training and outreach activities.

5.6 Implementation and future challenges

This document describes the efforts made to create SO protocols for the eLTER RI, and set them in context among the wider landscape of environmental monitoring. At the date of writing (late 2024), however, the SO protocols have not yet been implemented at the eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms and we see the need for continuously assessing the functioning of the SOs in the eLTER RI and be open to revisions. This will be especially important during the startup phase, when problematic issues will come to light and suggestions for improvements are anticipated.

Two key elements of this work will be Thematic Service Areas - TSA_02 Optimal Design as well as TSA_03 Technological Innovation and Development. TSA_02 will be responsible over the long term for regular revisions of methods and protocols, monitoring developments in methodology that could be adopted, as well as offering help and training for sites to implement them. It is important to note that this does not only cover iterative improvements to the initial list of SOs, but also adding new SOs as needed. Some variables that were identified as desirable to include could not be included in the initial list for a variety of reasons, but the intention is to revise these and incorporate them as new SOs at the earliest opportunity. A notable example of this is a range of aquatic biodiversity variables measured using “traditional” methods. The difficulties here are similar to those in the ground vegetation SO - a wide variety of national traditions associated with long-time series of existing data. In such cases, sites with already ongoing monitoring programs are strongly encouraged (Zacharias et al., 2024) to continue and submit data according to existing protocols (with harmonisation then being a challenge at database or end user level). Meanwhile, new sites should be equipped with a standardized version for aquatic biodiversity variables which will be part of the first revision of the SOs. TSA_03 will provide technical support for RI members on field calibration and observation maintenance. Further, the Thematic Service aims to make the SOs available for Earth Observation calibration and validation purposes allowing quality assurance for remote sensing data.

Another important feature of assessing and improving the performance of the RI that is related to the SOs will be checks on network coverage. During the setup of the RI, gap analyses identified key areas and habitat types that were underrepresented (Mollenhauer et al. 2018), and efforts were made to approach sites (and/or networks and RIs) that could fill these gaps. As the eLTER RI evolves, new sites and countries will join the network, and over time some will probably leave (although of course efforts should be made to prevent departures). This process of turnover will inevitably change the coverage of variables and habitat types and will in future motivate strategic approaches to other RIs and networks which have sites that could address these issues. This may bring new issues of standardisation and harmonisation similar to those faced during the setup phase, albeit on a smaller scale.

6 Conclusion

By aligning as closely as possible with existing standards, the eLTER RI aims to balance the need for comparability and integration with the flexibility required to accommodate site-specific contexts and legacy datasets. Key to this process has been the collaborative development of the SO Protocols, which were written through extensive consultation with experts, sphere leads, and the broader eLTER community. This process will continue with iterative improvements, ensuring that the protocols remain adaptable, and allowing for future revisions and expansions as new methodologies emerge or additional variables are identified. The eLTER RI's adoption of innovative approaches, such as WALLS, implements its commitment to capturing complex human-nature interactions across multiple scales. By leveraging established protocols from other research infrastructures while tailoring them to its unique needs, eLTER has laid a foundation for generating high-quality, standardised data essential for both research and informed policy-making. Looking ahead, the success of the eLTER RI will depend on its ability to continuously refine its protocols, foster cross-network collaboration, and address challenges related to data harmonisation and standardisation. The establishment of mechanisms for

revision (e.g., TSA02 Optimal Design) builds in responsiveness, supports the operational needs of the RI and positions eLTER as a leader in both environmental monitoring and whole ecosystem research.

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